

Does Corporate Acquisition Announcement Generates Abnormal Returns: An Analysis Using FF3 Model

Dr. Sunil Kumar

Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, Deen Dayal
Upadhyaya College (University of Delhi),

Abstract – A firm may undertake its business expansion through internal or external restructurings. The external restructuring includes, mergers, acquisitions, spin-off, and join-venture etc. Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A) are the most attractive and strategic business decisions which may influence stock-prices too. In India, every listed company is required to submit information in advance regarding such strategic actions to respective stock-exchanges under Regulations 30, of the SEBI, called corporate acquisition announcements (CA). Around the CA time, stock-price tends to change due to impact of such strategic actions. In the present study, event-study methodology is applied. The day on which CA is made is taken as $D=0$, and estimation window is considered from -83 to -7 days. Day 0 to +7 is taken as event window for which prediction of intercept and slope for R_i , R_m , R_f , SLM, and HMB is computed. For the purpose this study, four models, viz., market model, market model with Scholes-Williams Beta Estimation, CAPM and FF3F Models are applied. The results of first three models are not helpful in explaining model significantly and address impact of R_m and R_f on R_i . Whereas, FF3F model accounts size and value factors to investigate the impact of CA on ExR_i and AbR_i . CAPM establishes positive impact of CA on AbR_i on two days in post-CA period, but there is negative impact of CA on AbR_i during event-window under FF3F model.

Keywords - Corporate Announcement, Acquisition, Abnormal Return, French-Fama Three Factor Model.

I. INTRODUCTION

Corporate acquisition announcements (CA) refers to disseminating strategic information of a company to the stock exchanges. In India, as per Regulation 30 of Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) Listing Obligations and Disclosure Requirements (LODR) Regulations, 2023, every listed entity shall make disclosures of any events or information which, in opinion of the board of directors of the listed company, is material. These events are specified in Part A of Schedule III which includes acquisitions, scheme of arrangement, sale of disposal of any unit(s) etc. . The information under the above Regulation is displayed by the stock exchanges on its websites under the 'corporate announcement' tab. Nonetheless, such information is strategic in nature. Ferrier & Lee (2002) examined that changes in a company's stock price are related to changes in corporate strategy such as acquisitions, spinoffs and join ventures.

The business operations are important processes for firms to diversify their businesses to become stronger and more competitive (Lobo & Gomes, 2022). Mergers and acquisitions (M&A) are the external restructuring of the corporate to persuade expansion and wealth maximization. M&A are the utmost realistic way to speed up the growth enactment plan of companies (Wajid et al., 2022) through which companies can successfully scale up its development. But such strategies are legally and financially complex events, subject to risk, uncertainty, and information asymmetries (McCarthy & Noseleit, 2022). There is a number of studies focusing on the stock returns after the announcement date. It is, however, worthwhile to mention, that the majority of these studies investigated the phenomenon within the developed

markets, such as U.S. or Western European countries, while a number of studies involving the examination of emerging markets, like India, is very limited (Rani & Sangeeta, 2023) due to lack of comprehensive databases in emerging markets (Zaremba & Plotnicki, 2016a).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Martynova & Renneboog (2008) highlighted that announcement represents new information to the market, influences the expectations of the investors, with consequent impact on stock prices. Cohen & Qadan (2021) demonstrated that the information had a major impact on the acquirer's shares prices for 60 days after it was delivered to the financial markets. Simões et al.,(2012) took a sample from three Latin American countries and suggested that M&A convey a new information to the market in the form of announcement and contribute in value creation. They summarized that abnormal returns (AbR_i) were present in the event announcement and the following days. It is based on the possibility of AbR_i occurring as a result of some relevant event.

Wang et al. (2018) examined short-term wealth effect and highlighted that acquiring firms anticipate smaller returns than the target firms around the acquisition announcement date. On the contrary, Chaudary & Mirz, (2017) found that the acquiring firms experience negative returns but acquisitions do create AbR_i around the period of announcement. Pandey et al., (2022) studied the impact of CA on the stock returns during the pandemic stress. They found that CAs override the pandemic stress by influencing the stock prices. Verma & Kumar, (2023) found that in short-run resulting firms have a beneficial influence on share prices but majority failed to meet their

pre-M&A targets. It was discovered that investor prospective thinking about hope in the acquiring firm is a significant element in increasing the share price of the merging companies.

Nikolaos et al. (2007) analyzed that the effect of acquisition announcements on the abnormal returns of six Greek industrial and constructing firms. The results showed that the announcement ($t=0$) of an acquisition does not significantly affect the annual abnormal return (AAR) and cumulative annual abnormal return (CAAR). Although AAR is positive on day 0 and begins to decline right after that. They employed two dummy variables in the model indicating 'good news' and 'bad news'. Good news positively affects the average abnormal returns while the presence of 'bad news' has a slight negative effect. In addition, Chaudary & Mirz, (2017) argued that shareholders gain positive AbRi in the case of domestic acquisition; but vice-versa in cross-border acquisition.

Chaudary & Mirz, (2017) reveal that the market usually reacts positively to the M&A announcements. The shareholders of acquirer firms engaged in M&A experience a significant positive AbRi on the announcement day as well as cumulative average returns over small multi-days event windows around the announcements. However, a strong correction in the market price of the acquiring company takes place post-announcement and positive average returns do not sustain. Due to this correction, the cumulative abnormal average returns values turn negative during the post-event window. As per the findings of Rani et al., (2015), the most beneficial investment window for the investors is $(-5, 0)$, as the returns provided to the investors during this window are maximum.

Lobo & Gomes (2022) and MacKinlay (1997) suggested the event study methodology for M&A based on the previous estimation window and the event window. Campa & Hernando (2008) carried a study looking at the reaction by insiders, analysts and competing firms, to the announcement of M&As that took place in the European Union financial industry in the period 1998-2006. They applied event studies around the announcement date of the merger and analyzed that the stock market reaction of competing firms around mergers announcements differ between domestic and international mergers. Wajid et al. (2022) also applied event study methodology to examine abnormal returns of cross border acquisitions by Indian pharmaceutical firms of 24 acquisitions classifying 12 domestic and 12 transactions involving targets in the US and the UK. The study found that acquirers gained positive AbRi surrounding announcement of acquisition in US and UK.

An event study is a statistical method to assess the impact of an event on the value of a firm. The event methodology can be used to elicit the effects of any type of event on the firm action and magnitude of stock price changes. The

event study encompasses stock market responses to economy-wide events (e.g., regulatory changes) as well as corporate events (e.g., mergers, acquisitions, earnings announcement etc.) (Pavan et al., 2018).

(Reis, 2015) examined the stock market reaction and the announcements of company acquisitions for acquiring firms in the Turkish Stock Market during the period 1994-2013. Standard event study methodology is used to measure abnormal returns of acquiring companies during the announcement period. However, the study does not find any statistically significant evidence that cross-border acquisitions or a target's public status have any impact on the announcement period abnormal returns of the acquirer. Rani & Sangeeta, (2023) also applied event study approach to determine the AbRi and Cumulative abnormal return (CAR) taking estimation window and event window. They found that AbRi and CARs had negative results in majority of cases.

Bouzgarrou & Louhichi, (2014) highlighted a strong link between the choice of the means of financing and abnormal returns observed around the date of the event. Indeed, the difference of means test, the event study methodology and OLS regressions show that takeovers financed by debt outperform those financed by other means of financing. Moreover, it seems that the market reaction also depends on the legal environment, on acquirer specific factors and on acquisition characteristics. Abnormal returns fall for risky, high-growth bidders, and when target firm is from common law countries.

The simplest way to determine the coefficients of a model in order to find out expected results of the event window is one factor market model. This model is based on ordinary least square (OLS) estimations but has limitations. The methodology based on the procedures suggested by Scholes and Williams do seem to reduce biases in OLS estimates of beta (β_i) (Brown & Warner, 1985). The market model is the most commonly used model of expected returns in event studies and is the best supported by the evidence. As the CAPM and market model can produce different results, both should be used simultaneously (Armitage, 1995). Reinganum (1981) analyzed abnormal returns in small firm portfolios and argued that the simple one-period CAPM is an inadequate empirical representation of capital market equilibrium. He suggested that alternative models of capital market equilibrium should be seriously considered and tested.

Djajadikerta & Canterbury (2005) argued that three-factor model provides some improvement over the conventional one-factor CAPM in explaining the returns observed in the New Zealand stock market though the improvement is not significant as those reported in Fama and French (1993). Bello (2008) established that Fama-French three factor model is a remarkable improvement over the CAPM. Zaremba & Plotnicki (2016) applied CAPM, and FF3 Model and proves that an event-driven strategy based on

M&A deals may be successfully implemented in quantitatively managed portfolios with a regional focus. The study showed that the positive abnormal returns are decreasing while extending the time window.

Fama & French (1993) results mimic risk factors related to size and Book to Market Value (BE/ME) capture strong common variation in returns. These factors are proxy for sensitivity to common risk factors in stock returns. Fama French (FF) emphasized that size and book-to-market equity are related to economic fundamentals. Firms that have high B/M tend to have low earnings, conversely, low B/M is associated with persistently high earnings. Size is also related to profitability. Small firms tend to have lower earnings than big firms. They suggested that in event studies of the stock-price response to firm-specific information, the three factor regressions that include SMB and HML will do a better job isolating the firm-specific components of returns.

Using a three factors model is better than Sharpe-Linter model to judge post-merger stock returns of acquiring firms. Fama & French (1993) submitted that acquiring firms tend to be successful firms that have high stock prices relative to book value and low loadings on HML. In FF three-factor model, low loadings on HML reduce the average stock returns of acquiring firms and produce persistent negative abnormal returns in test that adjust only for market and size factors. It is empirically proved by Fama & French (1993) that three factor model (RM-RF, SMB, HML) is even simpler and does as well as the five-factor model.

Petkova (2006) investigated that FF factors HML and SMB are related to shocks in state variables that describe time variation in investment opportunities. He found that HML proxies for a term spread surprise factor in returns, while SMB proxies for a default spread surprise factor. The SMB and HML factors highlight the effects across industries better. The findings of Fama and French (1993) are very much country specific (Karp & Van Vuuren, 2017). However, Moerman, (2011) stated that there is a mixed evidence with respect to the relative performance of the different asset pricing models for the book-to-market and size-sorted portfolios. Indeed, the results from estimations of the linear CAPM and Fama and French (1993) three-factor models suggest that merger arbitrage returns are not significantly sensitive to market-wide factors (Maheswaran & Yeoh, 2005).

Basiewicz & Auret, (2010) tested the three-factor model of Fama and French (1993). They investigated that the spread in pricing errors between small and large firms, as well as value and growth, is reduced when compared with the base case, the risk adjustment with "traditional" models like the CAPM. There was a considerable improvement in the explanatory power when size and book to market factors were combined with the market factor. The various combinations of market factor with SMB and HML factors

were also found good at many places to explain the return behavior of stock prices (Mehta & Chander, 2010), statistically speaking, to predict the pricing errors left behind by the FF3F model. (Sehgal & Balakrishnan, 2013) confirm the presence of strong size and value effects in Indian stock market. FF three factor model is proved to be a better descriptor of returns on company characteristic sorted portfolios compared to one factor CAPM.

From the above literature review, it could be understood that event study methodology is appropriate to estimate intercept (α) and slope (β) to find out ExRi for event-window in order to compute AbRi. As suggested by the past studies that more than one model may be applied simultaneously in observe the impact of CA on ExRi and AbRi during event-window. Following the pattern of literature review the objectives and methodology of the research is set in the next part of the present study.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Objectives of the Study: The key aim of the study is to examine the impact of corporate announcement made by companies on its stock price around the announcement period. For that purpose, following objectives are proposed.

- To investigate the impact corporate announcement (CA) on stock price of the company.
- To study the impact of portfolio's return, i.e., market-return (R_m) and risk-free return (R_f) on the abnormal returns of the stock price during the event-window of the sample companies.
- To evaluate the abnormal returns of the sample companies by taking their size and book-to-market value into account.
- To examine the movement of stock price in the pre and post announcement period by taking AbRi under observation.

Hypotheses of the study: In the accomplishment of above stated objectives following hypotheses are devised.

There is no impact of CA on the stock price (Ri). Thus, the expected stock returns (ExRi) are equal to actual stock returns (AcRi) during the event window.

H1O: $ExRi = AcRi$ during the event-window.

H1A: $ExRi \neq AcRi$ during the event-window.

There is no impact of portfolio's return (R_m , R_f) on the abnormal return (AbRi) of the stock price (Ri) during the even-window.

H2O: R_m and $R_f \rightarrow AbRi = 0$.

H2A: R_m and $R_f \rightarrow AbRi \neq 0$.

The factors i.e., portfolio return (R_m-R_f), market-size (SMB) and book-to-market value (HML) do not have impact on the abnormal return (AbRi) of the sample companies during the event period.

H3O: R_m-R_f , SMB, HML $\rightarrow AbRi = 0$.

H3A: R_m-R_f , SMB, HML $\rightarrow AbRi \neq 0$.

The observed mean difference between expected returns (ExRi) and actual returns (AcRi) in the pre and post CA period is equal.

$$H4O: (Pre-CA \text{ ExRi} - AcRi) - (Post-CA \text{ ExRi} - AcRiAbRi) = 0.$$

$$H4A: (Pre-CA \text{ ExRi} - AcRi) - (Post-CA \text{ ExRi} - AcRiAbRi) \neq 0.$$

Sample Design and Data Extraction: The present study is empirical in nature and secondary data have been collected from the National Stock Exchange (NSE) India for the purpose of empirical analysis. The companies listed on the NSE and made corporate announcement during the financial year 1/4/2024 to 31/3/2024 are undertaken for the purpose of present study. Data extraction is started with 1357 announcements which filtered through the exclusion process and end with 60 companies. A number of 60 companies with one corporate announcement are shortlisted and classified into four categories, i.e., acquisitions, amalgamation, slump-sales (disposal), and others. However, the scope of present study is limited to acquisition only considering a suitable number of announcements for statistical applications. The sample design and data extraction are presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure-1: Sample Design and Data Extraction
Source: Authors' owned.

Data Organization and Theoretical Model: The date on which a company made announcement, on acquisition, is taken as Day=0. The data on the attributes/variables highlighted in Figure 3 are collected starting from Day -83 to Day +7. The period starting from -83 to -7 is taken as pre-announcement period and data of the same period is considered for the estimation (called estimation-window) in order to compute intercept (α) and beta (β). The time frame of -6 to 0 days excluded to avoid the impact of insider trading, if any. The time frame from 0 to +7 is set as event-window. The intercept and beta computed from the base of estimation window is used to predict stock return (R_i) of the sample companies from 0 to +7 period. The predicted results are called as expected returns (ExR_i). Afterwards, the expected returns (ExR_i) are deducted from the actual returns (R_i) of the period 0 to +7 in order to compute abnormal returns (AbR_i). Thus, $AbR_i = AcR_i - ExR_i$. The data organization and theoretical model of the study is presented through Figure 2 as given below.

Figure-2: Data Organization and Theoretical Model
Source: Authors' Owned.

Models for Analysis: In order to fulfillment of the research objectives, the data is analyzed with the help of four different models. The first model, viz., Market Model (MM) which predict the results for event window on the basis of intercept and beta estimator of market return (R_m). There are two alternative approaches to Market Model, (a) calculate the regression using the stock return (R_i) and market index return (R_m) during the same period Marsh, (1979), and (b) to introduce an additional

independent variable Dimson, (1979); Scholes & Williams, (1977) which could represent average or minimum return of the market. The limitation of MM is that it does not considered risk-free return into account which is essential in order to find out exact abnormal returns, thus Market Model with Scholes-Williams Beta Estimation (MMSW) is applied wherein two independent variables, i.e., R_m and R_f regress the expected returns in addition to intercept and standard error. For the purpose of R_f , the Nifty 10 years Benchmark G-Sec (Clean Price) Index is used as proxy considering its stability in terms of returns. This index is constructed using the clean price of 10 years bond issued by the Central Government of India. The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) is propounded by Sharpe (1964), Lintner (1965) and Mossin (1969) hypothesizing expected return on a stock asset with risk of the asset in an equilibrium market condition. The model observed the expected value on the basis of historical value. In CAPM, beta value greatly affects the expected returns of a securities. It establishes a positive relationship between the beta and the expected returns of securities (Sembiring et al., 2016). Thus, CAPM is applied which undertakes portfolio's return ($R_m - R_f$) to estimate ExR_i and AbR_i . Hence,

$$R_i = R_f + \beta(R_m - R_f) + \epsilon$$

Marc (1981) suggested that CAPM is an inadequate description of the behavior of real-world capital markets. The most serious source of the misspecification seems to relate to the size of a firm. The small size firms systematically earn abnormal returns (Reinganum, 1981b). The power of SBM-HML regression model is very fragile in comparison of single or two factors model (Sharma & Mehta, 2013); (Sehgal & Balakrishnan, 2013). As CAPM does not account size-risk and value-risk, therefore, French-Fama Three Factors Model (FF3M) is exercised to avoid the limitations of CAPM. The undertaken models along with attributes and regression equation is shown in the Figure-3 presented below.

Figure-3: Models used in the study.

Source: Authors' owned.

The natural log of return rate [(current data – previous data)/current data] is computed on all variables R_i , R_m , and R_f with the help of MS-Excel application.

Classification of SMB and HML: For the purpose of FF3M, the data market capitalization variable depicts market-size risk; and variable, book-to-market value, indicate value-risk; have been collected for sample companies for estimation-window and test-window from NSE-website. The market capitalization data is arranged in ascending order. In order to compute the breakeven point to classify firms, median (M) is computed (FAMA & FRENCH, 1995). The companies whose market-capitalization (MC) is more than median value are grouped under “B” and otherwise “S”. The term “Big (B)” represents companies with big market-capitalization and “Small (S)” denotes companies with small market capitalization. In other words, $MC > M \rightarrow$ “B”, $MC < M \rightarrow$ “S”.

Further, the value-risk is measured through Price-Earnings (P/E) ratio of the sample companies. P/E ratio is taken proxy to Book-to-Market Value (B/M) ratio due to lack of data on B/M ratio on sample companies. In studies of western countries, data on B/M ratio is taken from the database provided by Kenneth R. French Data Library which might not represent Indian economic scenario, therefore P/E ratio is taken as proxy to B/M ratio as suggested by Asness et al., (2013; Fama & French, (2006); and Novy & Marx, (2013).

The sample companies are grouped into “Low (L)”, “Medium (M)”, “High (H)” categories on the basis of P/E ratio. For that purpose, 30th and 70th percentile (Fama & French, 2012a; Martinez-Blasco et al., 2023) is calculated by through MS-Excel by using percentile “pth” [=percentile.inc(data array, 0.3), and =percentile.inc(data array, 0.7)] formulas.

A company with $P/E < 30$ th percentile grouped as “L”, If a company has 30 th percentile $< P/E < 70$ th percentile then labelled as “M”, otherwise, If $P/E > 70$ th percentile then marked as “H” From the above, sample companies are classified as per size and B/E value in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Classification of Sample Companies on the Basis of Size and B/M Value

Classification			Book to Market Value		
			Below 30%	Between 30% and 70%	Above 70%
			L	M	H
Size	Below 50%	S	SL	SM	SH
	Above 50%	B	BL	BM	BH

Source: Authors’ owned, formulated as per FF3 Model requirement. All sample companies then congregated as shown in Table 2 here under.

Table 2: Sample Companies Portfolios on the basis of SMB and HML

Sl	Sm	Sh	Bl	Bm	Bh
Bajajhind	Hcc	Kpil	Hdfcbank	Mphasis	Tvsmotor
Uflex	Triveni	Vaibhavgb	Jsl	Aiaeng	Elgiequip
Zuariind	Arvind	Gokex	Jswsteel	Crisil	Titan
Jkpaper	Ushamart	Dcw	Infy	Trident	Bharatforg
Dbreality	Mpsltd	Jublipharma	Cipla	Yesbank	Bluestarco

Source: Authors’ owned.

The variable, for the purpose of FF3M, Small Minus Big (SMB) representing size-risk is calculated by difference of average of small and average of big companies as presented in the following equation.

$$SMB = \text{Average (SL, SM, SH)} - \text{Average (BL, BM, BH)}$$

HML (High Minus Low B/M Ratio Portfolio Return), also called as value factor, is computed for the purpose of value-risk. It is observed that on an average value stocks earn higher return as compared to growth stocks (Petkova, 2006) (FAMA & FRENCH, 1995). HML is calculated by taking bivariate dependent sort portfolio based on market-capitalization and B/M ratio (Djadjdikerta & Canterbury),

2005; Fama & French, 2012b; Sehgal & Balakrishnan, 2013) as stated below.

$$HML = \text{Average (SH, BH)} - \text{Average (SL, BL)}$$

Statistical Techniques and Software: The statistical models are already mentioned in Figure-4 above. All models are based on regression analysis where Ri is the dependent variable and Rm, Rf, SMB, HML are independent variables. All models are analyzed using R-Studio (R-4-3.3). R-Studio libraries, stated in Table 3, are used before applying syntax for respective models.

Table 3: R-Studio Libraries used in Analysis

Library(ies)	“dplyr”, “tidyr”, “broom”, “tidyverse”, “readxl”, “lavaan”, “lavaanPlot”, “lmtest”, “purrr”, “quantmod”, “PerformanceAnalytics”, “ggplot2”
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Source: Compiled by Authors.

Empirical Results and Analysis

The results are presented according to models as conceived in the above discussion. Firstly, the coefficients, i.e., intercept (αi) and beta (βi), are determined taking data of estimation window (-83 to -7 days) and later the same αi and βi values are used to predict the expected (ExRi) for test-window period. After computing the ExRi, it is compared with actual returns (AcRi) of the test-window in

order to find out abnormal returns (AbRi). Table 4 presents the coefficients of intercept and estimator along with Adjusted R-Squared and F-statistic of the model.

Market Model: The market model accounts Rm only for the purpose of intercept and estimators. The results of Market Model are discussed below.

Table 4: Estimation Results: Market Model

call: lm(formula = Ri~Rm, data=Estimation Window)					
Residuals	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-11.3752	-1.0538	-0.0967	0.9445	17.5806

Coefficients:	Estimate	Std.Error	t-value	Pr(> t)	
(Intercept)	0.143255	0.04271	3.338	0.0008***	
Rm	0.47686	0.01305	36.535	<2e-16***	
Residual standard error	2.025	Df	2248	F-statistic:	1335
Multiple R-squared:	0.3726	Adj. R-Squ	0.3723	p-value:	<2.2e-16***
Sign. Codes	0 '***', 0.001 '**', 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.'				

Source: Authors' owned, output of R-Studio on market model

Taking the coefficients value, the Ri for the event-window is predicted called expected return (ExRi) as below.

The market model suggests that the coefficients α and β of Rm has significant impact of Ri. The intercept value is 0.143 and P-value is 0.008 which is significant at 0 level. Similarly, β coefficient is also significant. The values of Ri are much derived from coefficients α_i and β_i of Rm. The market model explains 37.23% of the input variable. However, model value, f-statistic is significant.

$ExRi = 0.14325 + (0.47686 * Rm) + St. Error$
 The ExRi is compared with actual return (AcRi) for test-window. Further, abnormal return (AbRi) is calculated by taking difference of ExRi and AcRi. Paired sample t-test has been applied to compare AbRi in the pre-CA period with post-CA period, i.e., -5 days to +5 days. The results of paired sample t-test is presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Paired-Sample T-test: Event-Window (Market Model)

Days	Mean Difference	t. statistics	P-Value
(-Inf,-5]	0.470	1.318	0.192
(-5,-4]	0.509	1.217	0.234
(-4,-3]	-0.317	-0.806	0.427
(-3,-2]	0.297	0.742	0.464
(-2,-1]	0.529	1.492	0.147
(-1,0]	-0.957	-1.451	0.158
(0,1]	0.130	0.216	0.831
(1,2]	0.250	0.509	0.615
(2,3]	0.250	0.662	0.513
(3,4]	-0.099	-0.176	0.862
(4,5]	0.748	1.832	0.077
(5, Inf]	1.112	3.281	0.003**

p-value is significant at 0.05 level

Source: Authors' owned, output of R-Studio on paired sample t-test.

Table 5 depicts that no mean difference has been observed between AbRi in pre and post CA period, except the 0+5 day. However, a lag of 5 days may not be considered as vital as it could have been either in continuation or closer to announcement date. The visuals on actual Ri and ExRi of all sample companies are presented through Figure 4 as below.

Figure 4: Ri and ExRi of the Sample Companies during Test-Window of Market Model

Source: Authors' owned, output generated in R-Studio
 Figure 4 demonstrates actual return (Ri) and expected return (ExRi). The results of said variables are shown from -6 to +6 days period of the test-window. The time (days) are shown on horizontal axis and return value is presented

on vertical axis. It is evident from the above that Ri is not much deviated from the ExRi which resulted into insignificant change in AbRi during the test-window except in case of Arvind, Cipla, HCC and Infy. But overall impact of corporate announcement found insignificant.

MMSW model incorporates an additional independent variable in the normal regression equation to estimate intercept and beta estimation. This additional variable represents minimum (or average) returns of the market index (Rm). The results of the MMSW is presented hereunder.

Market Model with Scholes-Williams Beta Estimation (MMSW)

Table 6: Market Model with Scholes-Williams Beta Estimation in R-Studio

call: lm(formula = Ri~ Rm + Rf, Data=Estimation Window (MMSW))					
Residuals	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-11.1530	-1.0633	-0.1023	0.8939	18.0839
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t-value	Pr (> t)	
(Intercept)	0.17148	0.03763	4.557	5.39e-06***	
Rm	-0.06907	0.05334	-1.295	0.195	
Rf	0.56604	0.05490	10.311	<2e-16***	
Residual standard error	2.073	Df	2248	F-statistic:	666.1
Multiple R-squared:	0.3014	Adj. R-Squ.	0.301	p-value:	<2.2e-16***
Sig. Codes:	0 '***', 0.001 '**', 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.'				

Source: Authors' owned, output of R-Studio on MMSW. Table 6 highlights the results on MMSW. The coefficients α and β of Rm and Rf are computed. The t-statistics value of intercept i.e., α is 4.557 which is significant at 0.05 level. The model shows that Rm regressed the Ri negatively, however is not significant. The t-statistics value of Rf is 10.311 significant at level 0.01 level. It also proves limitation of the simple market model with one independent variable as suggested by Dimson (1979) and Scholes, Williams (1977) that MM does not help in estimation of coefficient in significant manner. MMSW

model explains 30.1% of the variance as depicted through Adjusted R-Squared but it is significant at 0.05 level.

$$ExRi = 0.17148 + (-0.06907 * Rm) + (0.56604 * Rf) + St.Error$$

Following the above equation, ExRi were calculated in order to compute abnormal returns i.e., $AbRi = AcRi - ExRi$ for the test-window. The results on AbRi are analyzed using paired sample t-test as presented below in Table 7.

Table 7: Paired Sample T-test: Event-Window (Scholes-William Model)

Days	Mean Difference	t-Statistics	P-Value
(-Inf,-5]	0.256	0.790	0.432
(-5,-4]	0.285	0.734	0.469
(-4,-3]	0.124	0.275	0.786
(-3,-2]	-0.163	-0.363	0.719
(-2,-1]	-0.083	-0.149	0.882
(-1,0]	0.380	0.840	0.408
(0,1]	0.474	2.383	0.023**
(1,2]	0.689	-0.159	0.042**
(2,3]	0.249	0.650	0.521
(3,4]	-0.092	2.125	0.875
(4,5]	0.481	1.032	0.311
(5, Inf]	0.502	1.046	0.304

p-value is significant at 0.05 level

Source: Authors' owned, output of R-Studio on paired sample t-test.

Table 7 states the results of abnormal return during event-window. It shows that the abnormal returns on 0+1 and 0+2 days were significant at 0.05 level. The observed difference mean value is positive and significant for these two day which shows that sample companies gain for a short-period of two days only. The trend lines of ExRi and AcRi are presented in Figure 5 as follows.

Figure 5: Ri and ExRi of the Sample Companies during Test-Window for MMSW Model.

Source: Authors' owned, output generated in R-Studio
Figure 5 shows that Ri of KPIL, DBREALTY, JBLPHARMA were gained AbRi in comparison of ExRi immediate after the corporate announcement but last for two days only. For the remaining days of the test-window, no significant difference has been found in two returns.

4.3. Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM): As discussed in research methodology section that CAPM is associated with market risk, and average risk in equilibrium conditions. The average risk assures the minimum return on a stock portfolio. Thus, Rm represents market risk and Rf is the assured return in the form of debt/ gilt securities. Table 8 highlights the results on estimation window as below.

Table 8: Capital Asset Pricing Model Results in R-Studio

Call: lm(formula=Ri ~ Rm-Rf, Data=Estimation Window)					
Residuals:	Min	IQ	Median	3Q	Max
	-11.3752	-1.0538	-0.0967	0.9445	17.5806
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std.Error	t-value	Pr(> t)	
(Intercept)	0.14255	0.04271	3.338	0.000859****	
Rm-Rf	0.47843	0.01305	36.535	<2e-16***	
Residual Standard Error	2.025	Df	2248	F-Statistic	1335
Multiple R-squared:	0.3736	Adj. R-Squa	0.3723	P-value:	<2.2e-16
Sign. Codes:	0 '****', 0.001 '**', 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ''				

Source: Authors' owned, output of R-Studio on CAPM.
The coefficients intercept (α) and beta (β) value of the regressor ($R_m - R_f$) are 0.14255 and 0.47843 respectively. Both coefficients are significant at 0.05 level. It shows that ($R_m - R_f$) significantly impact the ExRi in the event-window. The following equation is formed by taking

values of the above coefficients into account in order to obtain ExRi.

$$ExRi = 0.14255 + 0.47843 (R_m - R_f) + S. Error$$

The abnormal returns i.e., $AbRi = Ri - ExRi$ is computed and compared by applying paired sample t-test. The test results are presented in Table 9 as follows.

Table 9: Paired Sample T-Test: Event-Window (CAPM)			
Days	Mean Difference	T-Statistic	P-Value
(-Inf,-5]	0.1554	0.4342	0.6657
(-5,-4]	0.2546	0.6101	0.5466
(-4,-3]	-0.6175	-1.6004	0.1204
(-3,-2]	0.0166	0.0416	0.9671
(-2,-1]	0.2616	0.7281	0.4724
(-1,0]	-1.2019	-1.8164	0.0797
(0,1]	-0.1384	-0.2287	0.8207
(1,2]	-0.0271	-0.0540	0.9573
(2,3]	-0.0424	-0.1119	0.9117
(3,4]	-0.3773	-0.6587	0.5153
(4,5]	0.4690	1.1532	0.2582
(5, Inf]	0.8766	2.5847	0.0150**

p-value is significant at 0.05 level

Source: Authors’ owned, output of R-Studio on paired sample t-test.

Table 9 demonstrates that there is no value of observed mean difference is significant except day 5 onwards which is not vital as there is a lag of 5 days after the day of CA. Thus, expected return is equal to actual return i.e., $ExR_i = R_i$ which means CA has not impact on stock returns during event period. The pictorial view of ExR_i and R_i are presented in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6: R_i and ExR_i of the Sample Companies during Test-Window for CAPM.

Source: Authors’ owned, output generated in R-Studio

It is observed from the Figure 6 that R_i in case of ARVIND, BAJAJHIND, CIPLA, HCC, INFY, JSL, USHAMART differ from ExR_i but has no significant difference as suggested by paired sample t-test results.

4.4. FF3 Model: In above, it is discussed that CAPM does not account for size risk and value risk, thus FF3 model is incorporated in the present research to explore the likelihood of abnormal returns by adding two more variables viz., SMB and HML representing size risk and value risk. Table 10 highlights the results of FF3 model and exhibits coefficients of intercept and slope of $(R_m - R_f)$, SMB and HML.

Table 10: FF3 Model Results in R-Studio

call: lm(formula = $R_i - R_f \sim R_m - R_f + SMB + HML$, data = Estimated Window)					
Residuals:	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-12.0147	-1.7277	-0.1058	1.4528	10.1988
Coefficients:	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	
(intercept)	0.9876	0.3792	2.604	0.0112*	
$R_m - R_f$	0.6897	0.5133	1.344	0.1833	
SMB	0.9603	0.376	2.554	0.0128*	
HML	-1.5766	0.1869	-8.435	2.61e-12***	
Residual standard error	3.085	Df	4498	F-statistic	29.2
Multiple R-squared	0.5523	Adj. R-Squ	0.5334	p-value	2.08E-12
Sig. Codes:	0 '***', 0.001 '**', 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 0.2 ' '				

Source: Authors’ owned, output of R-Studio on FF3 Model.

The intercept (α) and slope coefficients (β_i) of market risk ($R_m - R_f$), size risk (SMB), and value risk (HML) 0.9878, 0.6897, 0.9603, and -1.5766 respectively. All coefficients are significant at 0.05 level except the market-risk. However, the HML regress the R_i negatively but significantly. Adjusted R-Squared is 0.5334 which means that FF3 model explains 53.34% information which is significant at 0.05 level as well as highest explaining value in comparison of MM, MMSW and CAPM. It is evident that FF3 is must robust model in comparison of earlier ones.

On the basis of above coefficients, following equation is framed to calculate the ExR_i for FF3 model.

$$ExR_i = 0.9878 + 0.6897*(R_m - R_f) + 0.9603*(SMB) + (-1.5766)*(HML)$$

Further, the results extracted from ExR_i are compared with R_i of event-window in order to find out AbR_i of the event-window. A comparison of ExR_i and R_i is made and

analyzed with the help of paired sample t-test. The results of the same are shown in Table 11 below.

Table 11: Paired Sample T-test: Event-Window (FF3 Model)			
Days	Mean Difference	T-Statistic	P-Value
[-Inf,-5]	-1.9753	-3.2069	0.0022**
[-5,-4]	-2.3943	-2.5849	0.0150**
[-4,-3]	-3.0008	-2.8949	0.0071**
[-3,-2]	-2.1409	-2.2461	0.0325**
[-2,-1]	-2.4070	-2.4005	0.0230**
[-1,0]	-2.0098	-2.0228	0.0524*
[0,1]	-4.0595	-4.9970	0.0000**

[1,2]	-2.4345	-2.9243	0.0066**
[2,3]	-2.4346	-2.9084	0.0069**
[3,4]	-2.5893	-3.0781	0.0045**
[4,5]	-2.5938	-2.9272	0.0066**
[5, Inf]	-0.7175	-0.8007	0.4298

(**) p-value is significant at 0.05 level, (*) p-value is significant at 0.1 level

Source: Authors' owned, output of R-Studio on paired sample t-test.

Table 11 reveals the observed mean difference of the ExRi and Ri of the event-window which is negative from -5 to +5 days. T-statistics of the same are significant at 0.05 level of all days except the day -1 to 0 which is significant at 0.1 level.

The test value after 5th day is not significant. An observation from the above is that CA has adverse impact on actual Ri in pre and post commencement.

A significant impact during pre-CA event-window also an indication of insider trading. In other words, a significant lower Ri than ExRi is beyond to hypothesis (null) of no mean difference between Ri and ExRi. A pictographic view of the ExRi and Ri is displayed in Figure 7 hereunder.

Figure 7: Ri and ExRi of the Sample Companies during Test-Window for FF3 Model.

Source: Authors' owned, output generated in R-Studio
It is cogently visible from the Figure 7 that actual Ri is diverse from the ExRi during event-window. The fact is also sustained by paired sample t-test values as actual Ri trend lines are below to ExRi trend line in most of cases and days. Since the sample of 30 companies were classified into six sub-parts therefore it is imperative to compute paired sample t-test for the event-window sample-wise. The results of the same is displayed in Table 12 below.

Table 12: Sample-Wise Paired Sample T-Test

	BH	BL	BM	SH	SL	SM
Mean Difference	-2.564	-3.195	-2.985	-1.957	-2.095	-1.436
Df	64	64	64	64	64	64
T-test	-3.854	-5.786	-4.5869	-3.01109	-4.304	-2.15
P-value	0.000	2.18E-07	2.15E-05	0.003	5.87E-.05	0.04

p-values are significant at 0.05 level

Source: Authors' Owned.

The results of sample-wise paired sample t-test are in confirmation to overall results of the sample companies. However, it is crucial to note that the observed mean difference signifying abnormal return i.e., $AbRi = Ri - ExRi$ are negative which indicates that CA has adverse impact on actual return (Ri) during the event-window. Thus, no difference has been detected on the ground of size and value risk variable separately, but at the same time

these two variables unveiled the impact of CA on Ri in detailed manner in comparison of previously discussed models.

In order to confirm the results of FF3 model, the data is further analyzed using Wald Test, Sign Test and Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test. The results are presented below in Table 13.

Table 13: Results of Wald, Sign and Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test

Wald Test		Sign Test		Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test	
Res.Df	74	Estimate	0.661538	V	56904
Df	-3	Statistic	258	P-Value	<2.2e-16***
F-test	29.1976	P-Value	1.72E-10***	Alternative	

Pr(>F)	2.08E-12***	Parameter	390	hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
		Exact binomial test (two sided)		

P-value(s) significant at 0.05 level.

Source: Authors' owned, output of above tests from R-Studio.

Table 13 states the statistical results of Wald Test, Sign Test, and Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test. These tests are carried on to analyze whether the $ExR_i = Ri$ of the event-window in addition to FF3 Model. Null hypothesis of the Wald Test is that a set of parameters is equal to some value. For the purpose of present research use of Wald Test is to investigate whether coefficients of ExR_i and R_i are same and their difference is equal to zero. As the test value is significant so, null hypothesis will be rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted which state that there is change in the coefficients of ExR_i and R_i during the event window. Thus, the $ExR_i \neq Ri$ hence abnormal returns exist during the said window.

Sign Test and Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test are non-parametric statistical technique to make comparison of two related samples. These tests are alternative to parametric statistical tool like, paired sample t-test. The statistical values of both tests are also significant, and $R_i < ExR_i$ in test-window period which established that there is no gain in AbR_i after CA made by companies. In addition, a decline in AbR_i in pre-CA period indicates bearish trend in these stocks may be due to insider trading effect.

IV. CONCLUSION

From the above discussion it is summarized that in single factor model R_m is regress results of ExR_i of event-window significantly but no abnormal return is gained by the stockholders after acquisition. In Scholes-William Beta Estimation and CAPM, R_f and $R_m - R_f$ have significant impact in determination of ExR_i respectively. In case of, Scholes-William Beta Estimation model, the experience of AbR_i is for a short-time only i.e., for two day after the announcement of acquisition. No mean difference is observed in case of CAPM. Therefore, it could be said that single factor model and two factors models have limited application in prediction of ExR_i and calculation of AbR_i during event/prediction window. The size and value factors have significant impact in regressing ExR_i of estimation window and therefore AbR_i . FF3F model presents that the ExR_i are different from Actual R_i but CA has negative impact on R_i during event-window. The observed mean difference is negative during event-window from -7 to +7 days. It can be concluded that FF3F model is helpful in determination of AbR_i by classifying exogenous variable on the basis of market risk, size and value. The results are alike to (Bello, 2008b; Djajadikerta &

Canterbury), 2005; Reinganum, 1981b; Zaremba & Płotnicki, 2016b) contrary to Chaudary & Mirz, (2017); Rani et al., (2015); and Wajid et al., (2022)

The findings of the research may be helpful for stakeholders in taking decision that corporate announcement has same impact of all companies irrespective of their size and value. But, corporate announcement impacts negatively to stock prices. Since, there observed mean difference is negative in pre-announcement period also which indicates that stockholders has impression of decline in stock-price after the announcement which ripple down to post-announcement period too. The present study may be extended to other types of external restructuring by taking more independent variables into account and making comparison of different set of companies e.g., national and cross-border transactions.

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